

Keywords:

#Data, #OpenScience, #Reliance, #Geohazard, #ResearchDataManagement, #ResearchObjects, #EOSCinPractice

ROHub: A Resource Organization Service for Scientific Investigations

Facilitating Reproducibility, Reuse, and Citation of Research Materials and Methods

The Project Involved

Reliance (Research Lifecycle Management Technologies for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus Users in EOSC) is a H2020 project funded with Grant Agreement No.101017501. The objective of the project is to extend the research-enabling capabilities of EOSC with services for research lifecycle: the Research Objects (ROs) as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research resources, the data-cubes for scalable structured data access and discovery, and text mining services to extract machine-readable metadata from ROs.

The Research Community

Geohazard is a worldwide research community devoted to the study and management of natural hazards such as volcanic eruptions and earthquakes. Working in this domain implies field work to install instruments, the use of Earth Observation monitoring systems, simulation of potential hazards and direct interaction with decision makers and stakeholders.

The Challenge

Geohazard community is a global community dealing with scientific problems with fragmentation, unequal access to data and research methods, and isolation. This is critical as volcanic eruptions or similar natural disasters can impact neighbouring countries and even entire continents. The main challenge faced by Geohazard therefore is to create services that can ease access to data and tools, conduct high-quality research, and share the findings. These services should provide timely and scientifically accurate information about volcanic and seismic activity, not only within the research community but also to various end-users and stakeholders at national, European, and international levels.

Elisa Trasatti

Senior Geophysical Researcher
Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e
Vulcanologia, Italy – RELIANCE

"The RO service helps to organize resources, materials, and methods of an investigation. Share research materials with other scientists, facilitate reproducibility and reuse of scientific methods. Be recognized and cited (uniquely identified by an URI, or a DOI). Preserve results and prevent decay. Provide evidence to findings claimed in scholarly articles."

EOSC service or tool used

There are several services available via EOSC that can be used for the challenges mentioned. One example is the EGI notebooks, used through the Reliance Virtual Organization, which are useful to access data, to run tools, and share data, methods and results in the cloud with other colleagues. The RO service provided through the ROHub portal is also extremely significant to help organise and describe resources, materials, and the methods of an investigation. In particular with ROHub it is possible to:

- Share research materials with other scientists and end-users;
- Facilitate reproducibility and reuse of scientific methods;
- Be recognized and cited (uniquely identified by an URI, or a DOI);
- Preserve results and prevent decay;
- Provide evidence to findings claimed in scholarly articles.

The service has been leveraged to the EOSC marketplace during the H2020 Reliance project. <https://tinyurl.com/5h4u8mfr>

Useful tips & tricks

The RO paradigm can be used to document research activity in several ways: to share Earth Observation data products (e.g., the Changbaishan volcano¹, China/North Korea, surface deformations), to timely share reports and materials (e.g., during the volcanic emergency of the Nyiragongo volcano², DR Congo), and to fully document a published tool (VSM, Volcanic and Seismic source Modelling³ with links to the code and to examples, the latter being themselves ROs).

1. <https://doi.org/10.24424/vfp6-r230>
2. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/45841548-0362-4aea-80f2-ea71d81a691f>
3. <https://doi.org/10.24424/t83f-5t97>

Keywords:

#Data, #OpenScience, #Reliance, #Geohazard,
#ResearchDataManagement, #ResearchObjects,
#EOSCinPractice

Benefits and impact

During the 21-22 May 2021 eruption of the Nyragongo volcano (DR Congo), my team and I have been promptly working analyzing Earth Observation data (Sentinel-1) to map surface deformations, and running modelling tools to undisclosed the position and depth of the magma feeding the eruption. The RO service in the EOSC allowed me to rapidly share our scientific information not only among the Geohazard global community, but also to international end-users and stakeholders, confident that, even in the midst of an emergency, IPR was properly attributed. The benefit of using the EOSC service is not only cross-disciplinary, but goes beyond the scientific community domain.

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC is an infrastructure that can be used by researchers and practitioners of any scientific discipline. There is a large suite of services available that can improve how the research is carried out, and therefore boost the results sharing. For example, during the Reliance project it has been possible both to use a EOSC service (the EGI notebooks and cloud), and to implement new services, such as the ROs, the data-cube for Earth Observation data access and discovery, and the text-mining service.

Across disciplines

By definition, the RO service is used to document any type of resource of the research lifecycle, therefore it can be widely used in any domain and is cross-disciplinary by nature. In addition, among the different tools available to document the RO, it is possible to create relations among the current RO and others.

Useful material related to this story

reliance-project.eu

Liked this
#EOSCinPractice
story?

Follow
@EOSCFuture
for more!

Share your own #EOSCinPractice story here